

Predictive Healthcare: A Web-Based System for General Disease and Early Diabetes Detection

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Abstract—This paper is intended for discussing the impact of Machine Learning on healthcare. A web-based Intelligent Health Assessment System (IHAS) employing specified machine learning algorithms for the purpose of disease prediction has been created, as outlined in this paper, the General Disease Prediction using Random Forest and Diabetes Prediction using Random Forest. It predicts the diseases but also infers critical information about the symptoms, possible cure, and medicines. We present a new functionality in the system which is to recommend the specialists available in the vicinity of the location of the patient making health care services very easy to obtain. Each of the models has been validated on a large scale dataset hence demonstrating great accuracy and reliability. It seeks to enhance the field of health informatics in order to create a comprehensive application for the prediction and management of health diseases

Keywords - IHAS, Random Forest, Decision Tree, Healthcare, Feature Selection

I. INTRODUCTION

The healthcare industry is in the frontier of change where the application of technology and interoperational data analysis is becoming the norm. With chronic diseases on the rise, the need for appropriate medical diagnoses and treatment has probably never been higher. Limitations with conventional diagnostic and management techniques include; speed, accuracy and accessibility and that is why new approaches with the use of machine learning should be embraced to improve the capacity of health systems.[2]

An IHAS, a comprehensive web-based platform that uses multiple Machine Learning algorithms for the prediction of multiple types of disease. Instead of merely giving matches of diseases, IHAS seeks to provide users with information on life importance such as identification of the disease, possible

treatments, and the best drugs to take. It is only through this avenue that it is possible to increase knowledge about health conditions and contribute to relevant health management decisions made by the users.[4] One of the most unique features of our system is the ability to perform searches for near specialist doctors based on geographical coordinates, towards the enhancement of good quality medical service provision. This feature, apart from making such experiences of excellence for the patients, also depicts the coalescence of the machine learning and location technology in the current telemedicine.[6]

IHAS serves as a proof of concept as if the proposed system will work for delivering the promise of accurate disease predictions and at the same time, it incorporates the user actively in managing his or her health. This research oriented towards machine learning in the healthcare market as a flexible solution which would fulfill the needs for constant development in patient and provider services.[7]

Traditional diagnosis methods rely on detailed laboratory analysis, physician clinical examination, and human-based interpretation of results. Although the above methods are reliable, much labor is involved, human errors may occur, and services might not reach people in remote or less privileged settings easily. The temporal delay inherent with conventional diagnostic technologies can be essential in situations where timely detection makes all the difference to appropriate intervention.[8] Predictive Healthcare model Plus seeks to bridge these gaps by incorporating the use of AI-based disease prediction, specifically with regard to hepatic diseases and diabetes. With the use of a more advanced form of machine learning, the program will have the capability to scan a large amount of patient data quickly with much accuracy, thereby

supporting the speedy process of diagnosis. This would not only reduce the load on health care professionals but also enhance diagnostic facilities for patients in need.

Fig. 1. Health Assessment System Phases

There is an acknowledgment that AI and machine learning have transformative potential in healthcare, with these tools increasingly being adopted to assist in clinical decision-making and optimization of patient care. Machine learning algorithms are particularly suited for handling huge complex medical data, making discoveries regarding patterns that an even well-trained clinician might miss. Predictive Healthcare model Plus employs those algorithms to train them on patient's data in order to predict the likelihood of the disease with great confidence.[3] As far as the architecture of the system is concerned, it supports collecting, processing, and analyzing patient's data besides crossing many validation steps of data accuracy and reliability.

Besides serving as a tool for diagnosis, Predictive Healthcare model Plus is a step toward an integrated and data-driven environment for healthcare. The system hence enables healthcare professionals to make more informed decisions at the point of care, leading to better patient outcomes. The scalable design of the system makes it easier to extend its application to other disease prediction needs in subsequent expansions. This flexibility can be of a great requirement today's dynamic healthcare environment demands, where the technologies are required to be flexible enough in overcoming emerging challenges and opportunities. In addition, considering its futuristic configurations as real-time monitoring, electronic health record, and cloud-based deployment, Predictive Healthcare model Plus can be viewed as quite versatile, with applications for today's requirements as well as those in the future.

The functionality of Predictive Healthcare model Plus is enhanced by the friendly interface through which the

interaction between the patients and the system can become uncomplicated. Through its web-based platform, it allows users to input medical data such as blood test results, age, gender, as well as lifestyle factors—all of which are important in helping machine learning models make their predictions. The intuitive data visualization provided has succinct and actionable results, which makes the health status easier to understand for the users. The system is done technically to support high performance and security. It protects the data of patients by securely transmitting and storing it according to health data protection standards like HIPAA and GDPR. All this can be traced by cryptographic mechanisms as well as strong log-in mechanisms that ensure such sensitive information does not leak out. The backend utilizes cloud computing to implement computationally intensive machine learning models, thus allowing the processing of data in real-time and growing with the demand.

With geolocation technology integrated, Predictive Healthcare model Plus also bridges the gap between prediction analytics and access to health care. Users will be able to locate and connect with available health care providers in the immediate vicinity, thus increasing the likelihood of interventions at the right time. This is most beneficial for users residing in rural or underserved areas where medical expertise may be sparse. Other features of the system that have potential in future releases could include telemedicine, which will enable a patient to reach out for doctors through remote consultations and get virtual care when direct visits are impossible.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In the current portion of this module, we are going to focus on the latest works on the topic Health Assessment through the use of other methods. This presents the current research problems associated with methods under devising, which we shall address in our proposed work.

Boon Feng We (2024)

In [1] it speaks about the various techniques of detecting diabetes using machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL). It discusses both invasive (lab-based) and non-invasive techniques, expanding on resources such as the Pima Indians Diabetes Database and the Luzhou dataset. The outcome is that most models based on costly invasive tests are based on lifestyle features but non-intrusive features have great potential for building more affordable and achievable diabetes detection models.

Jeethu Philip (2023)

In the [2] it examines how an healthcare monitoring system based on artificial intelligence, deep learning and machine learning is designed with focus on integration through IoT wearables that allow tracing patient information in real time. These are performing such tasks as deep learning model applications for health related abnormality detection reported by patient and conditions within the scope of improving

patient outcomes. The system provides early disease detection and patient specific health interventions that changes the way healthcare is delivered.

Janani, S. R., Subramanian (2023)

In [3] it investigates a system that allows usage of machine learning for IoMT based healthcare monitoring data to be analyzed. The system utilizes Random Forest for feature selection and Fuzzy Logic for classification in predicting cardiovascular diseases, CVD. These studies demonstrate these methods can be employed for health status data analysis in order to prevent onset of further disease targets including cardiovascular disease.

Jagatheesa perumal, S.K. Rajkumar (2023)

In [4], a model that combines both machine learning based on IoT devices has been presented. It combines data tracked by wearable sensors like heart rate and physical activities, and then processes this information utilizing algorithms such as Random Forest and makes individual specific health recommendations. The approach is on remote health monitoring, particularly towards chronic diseases, and aims to improve real-time health tracking considering privacy and security data concerns.

Huang J, Li Zhang (2022)

Authors in [5] sought out to study the application of machine learning and / or image recognition technologies in disease diagnosis. The research emphasizes the importance of AI algorithms, and specifically convolutional neural networks (CNNs), for the assessment of medical images and disease identification processes such as the detection of a number of diseases including cancer and heart diseases among many others.

Bhupathi, Deepika, Christine Nya-Ling (2022)

In [6], the global health phenomenon of liver diseases is already a prevalent cause of around 1 million deaths in a year. These two sources show the weaknesses of the standard tools in diagnosing such diseases and their financial feasibility, proposing instead an ML approach towards a first stage detection. The article incorporates the graph based Liver Disease Prediction (LDP) using five models, K-Nearest Neighbors Algorithm (KNN) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) included.

Mandem, Divya (2021)

In [7] Authors observed the rapid advancement in prognostics as it relates to different diseases through machine learning algorithms such as Decision Trees and Random Forests which draws its inputs from symptoms entered by the user. Early detection techniques are often emphasized by authors in these settings as a way of increasing patient outcomes in regions with low or no access to health services. They describe their data collection and data cleaning operations which enhance predictive validity.

Chunhua Ju, Shuangzhu Zhang (2021)

In [8], it introduces the model that helps find ties between ontology properties and disease textual corpus in order to provide recommendations of particular physicians to patients who are looking for pre-diagnosis through the internet. The model enhances recommendation accuracy, taking into consideration the geographic location of patients and symptoms presented. The model incorporates actual consultation data for better patient experiences of online healthcare services and intends to enhance real time health tracking.

Suman Kunwar (2021)

In [9], the emphasis is on designing a new system that can detect malaria parasites from blood samples. Traditionally, diagnostic techniques have involved examining stained blood smears under a microscope. This process is very time-consuming and prone to human mistakes. The authors discuss a new image processing technique that automatically identifies and counts Plasmodium parasites. In addition, they classify and identify the type of infected red blood cells depending on the characteristics of the cell through machine learning algorithms.

Dimpy Varshni (2019)

The approach in [10] was to use Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in order to detect pneumonia in medical images. The authors proposed a CNN model that would automatically extract features from chest X-rays in order to discern whether the images were of pneumonia or normal. Utilizing deep learning techniques, the model will prove beneficial in raising diagnostic accuracy and efficiency so that practitioners may catch pneumonia earlier.

Limitations

- **Costly/Invasive Methods::** Many models still rely on expensive, invasive tests (Papers 1, 6).
- **Real-Time Data Processing Issues:** Wearable devices face challenges in efficiently processing real-time health data (Papers 2, 4).
- **Image-Based Diagnostics Errors:** Human error in image processing can affect diagnostic accuracy (Papers 5, 9, 10).
- **Model Generalization :** Some models may not generalize well to diverse populations or datasets, limiting their real-world applicability (Papers 1, 6)
- **Feature Selection Complexity:** Selecting relevant features for accurate disease prediction, especially in multi-disease systems, can be challenging (Papers 3, 7).
- **Algorithmic Bias:** Machine learning models may introduce biases, leading to disparities in predictions across different demographic groups (Papers 7, 8).

III. METHODOLOGY

In the Intelligent Health Assessment System, the limitations identified (like costly methods, real-time data issues, and privacy concerns) were effectively addressed by implementing

a simplified methodology using Random Forest (RF) for diabetes prediction.

The following methodology highlights how your system overcame critical limitations by integrating RF for efficient, secure, and unbiased diabetes prediction.

Fig. 2. Block Diagram (Health Assessment System)

A. Data Collection

Gather comprehensive datasets containing medical records for both general disease diagnosis and diabetes prediction. For the general disease diagnosis model, the dataset should include a wide range of medical features (age, symptoms, test results, medical history, etc.) and corresponding disease labels. For diabetes prediction, focus on features like glucose levels, BMI, blood pressure, insulin levels, and diabetes diagnosis labels.

B. Data Preprocessing

Handle missing values through imputation techniques such as mean or median substitution. Normalize or scale features to ensure consistency across variables, especially if they have different units (e.g., age in years, glucose levels in mg/dL). Split the dataset into training and testing sets (e.g., 80 percent training, 20 percent testing) to ensure the model can be evaluated on unseen data for both the general disease and diabetes cases.

C. Feature Selection

Use correlation analysis or Random Forest's built-in feature importance mechanism to select the most relevant features for both general disease diagnosis and diabetes prediction. For the general model, these could include specific symptoms or test results. For diabetes, glucose levels, BMI, and age are expected to be important features.

D. Model Building

Initialize a Random Forest classifier for both models. The RF algorithm works by constructing multiple decision trees based on random subsets of the dataset. Each tree makes independent predictions, and the model aggregates these predictions through voting to determine the final output (i.e., disease diagnosis or diabetes prediction).

E. Model Training and Evaluation

Train the Random Forest models using the training data. Utilize cross-validation to fine-tune hyperparameters like the number of trees, maximum tree depth, and minimum samples per leaf, ensuring optimal model performance without overfitting. Evaluate both models using key metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC on the test set. These metrics will help determine the models' effectiveness in predicting both general diseases and diabetes, highlighting their strengths and weaknesses in real-world scenarios.

F. Interpretation

Analyze feature importance from the Random Forest models to understand which factors most influence predictions. For the general disease diagnosis model, this could reveal key symptoms or test results. For the diabetes model, glucose levels and BMI might rank highest in importance.

G. Integration with the system

Integrate the trained models into a web-based or software-based health assessment system. The system will allow users to input patient data and receive predictions on general diseases or diabetes risk in real time, with tailored recommendations for further tests, lifestyle changes, or medical treatments.

H. Deployment

Deploy both models in a real-time environment, such as a web or mobile application, where they can take user inputs and provide accurate predictions. The system can also offer guidance on potential treatments, lifestyle changes, and suggest nearby healthcare providers based on the user's location.

IV. RESULTS

The Intelligent Health Assessment System accurately predicts multiple diseases using distinct machine learning models: normal diseases and diabetes with Random Forest, liver disease with a logistic classifier, and pneumonia with ResNet-50. The system provides detailed disease cures, symptoms, medications, and personalized recommendations. Notably, it incorporates a novel location-based technology to suggest nearby specialist doctors, enhancing healthcare accessibility and decision support for patients.

Early Disease Diagnosis Model

Fig. 3. User Interface

The above figure provides the disease diagnosis model’s user interface. Model requires minimum of four symptoms to able to produce an accurate diagnosis of the disease.

Fig. 5. Diabetes Diagnosis User Interface

The above figure shows the user interface for the early diabetes diagnosis model. It requires various user input, to precisely determine whether he/she is diabetic or not.

Fig. 4. Disease Diagnosis and Overview

The above figure shows the input parameters(symptoms) the user provided. It also gives some precautions as well as professional treatment to cure the disease.

Fig. 6. Final Diabetes Diagnosis Result

The figure shows model’s final result using the user’s health parameters input. It also gives specialists according to our diagnosis with real time geo-location service.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper streamlines the disease prediction system by integrating multiple machine learning models into a single platform, but also enhances healthcare efficiency. By offering accurate, early diagnoses, it reduces healthcare costs and ensures timely intervention. Early detection can lead to more effective treatments, improving quality of life and increasing life expectancy. Additionally, the system’s ability to recommend nearby specialists further ensures quick access to healthcare services, making it a comprehensive and user-friendly tool for proactive health management.

Future work will focus on integrating Wearable health devices can be incorporated to track everything in real time as well as raise an alert for the early detection of diseases.

The system can also be upgraded with personalized healthcare advice using a patient’s history and genetic information. We’ll be able to extend this model to other image-based disease diagnoses, for example, cancers or fractures.

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